

VANET Security: Solutions to Detect and Prevent Availability Attacks.

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Abstract—The type of network that exchanges data amongst automobiles with the goal of increasing road safety just and works in the same way as a Mobile Ad hoc network (MANET) works is called Vehicle Ad hoc network (VANET). Critical information shared between vehicles raises serious security concerns since the data transmitted over the vehicle network is sensitive and may have an impact on crucial security choices. However, because of the high mobility and enormous scale of VANET, it has grown vulnerable to attacks, particularly availability attacks, which make the network unavailable to users and pose a serious threat. This work primarily examines availability attacks, their forms, and the scenarios in which an attacker could launch one against VANET networks. This article also investigates various defenses against such attacks and how to identify and stop them.

Index terms- VANET; Availability; threat; Defense;

I. INTRODUCTION :

The Safety Control Department of Highway Traffic along with several investigating agencies and Transport Department of the U.S issued a public service announcement in 2016 [1].

The Safety Administration published a warning on cars' which are increasingly growing to remote exploits. A few examples of possible car cyber security attacks include deactivating the door locks, the brakes, and the engine. As automobiles become increasingly connected, they become a fresh target for hackers. Hackers can attack your car while it's on the road as long as they have contact with it. They may, nevertheless, occasionally be able to hack into it from a great distance.

Modern transportation systems are going through a great shift thanks to Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs), which are changing how automobiles interact and communicate with each other. These networks allow smooth communication between vehicles (V2V), vehicles and infrastructure (V2I), as well as other connected objects. They are an essential component of the larger Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem. [2]

Dedicated Short-Range Communication (DSRC) and cellular networks are two examples of wireless communication technologies that are used by automobiles to serve as mobile nodes in an ad hoc network called VANETs. The exchange

of vital information, such as traffic updates, road conditions, emergency alerts, and entertainment services, is made easier by this dynamic network, improving passenger satisfaction, road safety, and traffic efficiency.

II. VANET ARCHITECTURE:

Roadside units (RSUs), infrastructure, and automobiles are all connected via a complex architecture known as vehicular ad hoc networks, or VANETs, which enables smooth communication and information sharing on the highways. [3] Mesh networks serve as the foundation for VANET architecture, Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) communications are used in this. Starting with On-Board Units (OBUs) mounted in cars and outfitted with specialized short-range communication (DSRC) technology, the architecture consists of multiple essential parts. Within a specific range, these OBUs function as the communication nodes, allowing cars to connect with one another. In the meantime, V2I communication is supported by Roadside Units (RSUs), which are strategically placed infrastructure nodes that improve connection by granting access to services, disseminating information, and managing networks. [4]

Information sharing and cooperative driving functions are made possible by the multi-hop communication model used by the VANET architecture. Messages are passed through intermediary cars or RSUs to reach their destination. The foundation of VANET communication is provided by communication protocols like IEEE 802.11p/WAVE (Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments), which guarantee low latency and high-speed data exchange—both of which are essential for safety applications. [5]

The IEEE 802.11 standard's 802.11p/Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE) protocol is a subset created especially for communication in vehicles. It forms the foundation of what is usually referred to as Dedicated Short-Range Communications (DSRC) and runs in the 5.9 GHz frequency band. It is designed for use in vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communications [6].

Moreover, the architecture covers a great extent of applications, like infotainment, traffic efficiency, safety. VANETs are used by safety applications such as emergency

ensure the privacy of customer details, including online billing, user IDs, and other sensitive data. Potential threats to VANET privacy include data analysis, code spoofing, and eavesdropping. Safeguarding communications during processing or adjustment. [13] Ensuring unbroken communications between different VANET agencies is important. It ensures that the messages' confidentiality must be protected from outsiders. Threats such as Software Switch Attack, Masquerade Attack, and Repeat Attack undermine the credibility of emails. Enforcing an effective procedure is necessary to protect messages both during transmission and reception. VANET uses IEEE1609.2 requirements for security services. The security services and interfaces for Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE) communication are specified in IEEE 1609.2. [5] Its main objective is to define the architecture and security specifications needed to protect messages transmitted over vehicular ad hoc networks. Accountability threats include the difficulty in identifying and bringing to justice the parties in charge of security lapses or malicious actions occurring on the network. It is difficult to ensure accountability in the absence of methods for identifying and assigning actions to particular nodes. This might lead to malicious behavior remaining unpunished and possibly damage network trust. [5]

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW:

1. Availability Attacks:

In cybersecurity, availability attacks seek to interfere with the regular operation of networks, systems, or services and making them unavailable to authorized users. The availability part of the CIA (Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability) triad is the precise target of these assaults, which focus on preventing users from accessing resources or services. Denial-of-Service (DoS) or Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks are a common type of availability attack in which adversaries overwhelm systems or networks with excessive traffic or requests. Due to the overload of traffic, resources like memory, processing power, and bandwidth become blocked making the targeted services slow and unusable, to authorized users. Availability attacks can take use of application faults, network infrastructure vulnerabilities, or engineering defects that allow services to be overloaded. [12]

These hacking attempts can affect essential functions like banking, e-commerce, healthcare, and government systems in addition to interfering with company activities. They can also cause financial losses, harm to a company's reputation, and in some cases, even put public safety at danger, as in the case of VANET systems. Strict security measures, including as network monitoring, traffic filtering, access controls, and redundancy plans, must be put in place in order to prevent and mitigate availability threats and ensure service continuity

Fig 2. Attacks and Threats in VANET

even in the case of an attack. [11]

The kinds of availability attacks and threats against VANET systems, as well as suggested countermeasures, will be the main topics of this study.

A. Denial of Service Attacks:

In cybersecurity, a denial-of-service (DoS) attack seeks to

Distributed Denial of Services.

prevent authorized users from accessing networks or services by flooding them with a large number of requests or data. A DoS attack reduces resources, such as bandwidth or computing power, by flooding the target system with malicious traffic, making the service slow or unavailable. Attacks of this kind have the potential to stop vital processes, resulting in lost money, downtime, and a ruined user experience. [14] DoS attacks frequently take advantage of flaws in applications or network infrastructure, highlighting the significance of strong security measures to identify, stop, and reduce such malicious activity. Depending on the attacker's skills, the attack may target application services or network hardware infrastructure by taking advantage of vulnerabilities. This will have different impacts on the victims. To stop or identify attacks, one must be aware of the attackers' intentions and level of execution. [15]

In this denial-of-service attack, the attacker wants to overwhelm the nodes' capacity to carry out other crucial and essential functions. The node is always active, and every one of its resources to confirm the messages sent by the attacker.

Overwhelm of node resources

b) Distributed Denial of Services (DDoS):

Because DDoS attacks spread throughout the network, they are especially harmful when applied to automobiles. The attackers use a variety of locations to launch their attacks.

B. Black Hole Attacks:

A BHA is a type of service denial attack where a mischievous node entirely removes packets from the legal node. Without routing table consultancy, a mischievous node in BHA quickly answers with a fake RREP (Route reply) after receiving an RREQ (route request) from the node of origin. Figure 3 shows Impact of a BHA on VANET Network.

The shortest and most recent route in AODV (ad-hoc on-demand distance vector) is thought to be this RREP packet,

Fig 3. Impact of BHA on VANET.

DoS attacks on VANETs can be carried out in two different ways: by overloading node resources, or by packet loss. [16]

a) Overwhelm the Node Resources:

which has a minimum hop count value and a higher sequence number. [17] [18]. The source node starts sending data packets in the direction of the mischievous node after incorrectly reading the fake RREP packet as an ideal path. Such packets are dropped by a BHA rather than being sent to their intended location, which weakens network performance and security overall and blocks the flow of information throughout the network. These packets could include

important information messages that need to be sent out quickly and within a certain window of time, such as warnings, updates and emergency notifications. In a highly dynamic VANET, dropping such packets could cause accidents, traffic jams, fatalities, and congestion. [19]

C. Jamming Attacks:

In Jamming attack, the valid node will not be allowed to interact via messages from the jammed regions because the constant signals it receives show that the channel is always busy. A jamming attack lowers the packet delivery ratio (PDR) since the sender can send the packets successfully. When the jamming attack begins, the other nodes won't be able to receive the packet. The jammer attack can interfere with a variety of information including weather reports and accident reports. Figure 4 shows Jamming Attack In VANET. [20]

As seen, if the packets were not sent or received at the appropriate time, this attack might risk the passenger's life. The adversary's unrestricted mobility and lack of requirement for compliance to other protocols make it extremely difficult to stop them from joining the network. The radio transmitting power affects the network's jamming impact.

Based on their behavior, jamming attacks can be roughly classified into 4 major types [21], i.e.,

1. Constant Jamming: Regardless of whether the channel is idle or not, this kind of attack operates by continuously transmitting random bits over it.
2. Reactive jamming: In this kind, the attacker listens in on the channel continually, sending noise signals as soon as they detect any kind of broadcast.
3. Deceptive jamming: In this technique, the attacker continuously transmits an endless stream of random data, leaving no space between packet transmissions.
4. Random Jamming: In this case, the attacker creates a variation between the sleep and jamming modes in order to preserve network energy.

Fig 4. Jamming Attack in VANET.

V. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS:

All network needs to prioritize security, and as VANET grows quickly and becomes more useful, the significance of these security concerns grows as well. Since human lives are at risk in vehicular ad hoc networks, it is important to make sure that only real and valid data is shared over the network.

It is important that someone must defeat these attacks to create a secure environment. The methods for identifying and reducing them are covered in this section.

A. Denial of Service Attacks Detection and mitigation Techniques:

A Dos attack was carried out on VANET Network to look into the effect on network performance and assess the possible remedies and solutions in [22] [23].

The below code was used to carry out the attack.

```
# UDP FLOODING

set udp0 [new Agent/UDP]
$ns attach-agent $node_0 $udp0

set udp1 [new Agent/UDP]
$ns attach-agent $node_1 $udp1

$ns connect $udp1 $udp0

# Attack DOS
for {set i 0} {$i < 2000} {incr i} {
    $ns at [expr {$i * 0.01}] "$udp0 send 500 {DOS ATTACK PACKET!}"
}
```

The UDP type has been established for the transmitter and receiver channel, which is the one that exists between the sending and receiving agent nodes. They stand in for the

sender and recipient, who are in charge of sending and receiving messages. For a simulated duration of 20 seconds, the broadcast was carried out every 0.01 seconds.

The following code represents the reception:

```
Agent/UDP instproc process_data {size data} {
  global ns
  global udp0
  global udpl
  global dbans
  $self instvar node_

  # do nothing, simulating packet processing
  for {set i 0} {$i < 1000} { incr i } {

    $ns trace-annotate "[$node_ node-addr] received ($data)"
  }
}
```

The user is distracted by these fictitious communications because it mimics how long it requires to operate the messages from the invader. To restrict the pace at which messages are received, a rate-limiting method was suggested and tested on the attack simulation. Message reception limit control can be used to do this, giving control over the rate and consequently the quantity of messages received. This can

block data from flooding the network and make it easier for the system administrator to identify and halt the attack.

The interval of time between the arrival of the current message and the last message before it, is used to control the message limit. If the value exceeds the entered limit, the message will be ignored by the receiving node. As a result, the limit size needs to be carefully selected so that it is neither too small to prevent the arrival of legitimate and significant messages, nor too large to let the transmission of all attacker messages. Table 1 shows the improvement in the resistance to the attack. In order to evaluate the method of restricting the rate at which data packets are received, the test was rerun with (200m,5s) adjustments included in the code. In order to address the DoS issue following APDA, writers in [24] employed the RPDA technique as a fresh algorithm called the Request and Response Detection Algorithm (RRDA).

The principle behind this strategy is that a node that is inside A request is sent by the network area to the Roadside Radio Transducer (RSRT). The repository for vehicle validation and hop count is maintained by RSRT. Nodes are able to

	Before the attack	Effect of attack after applying the solution rate limit (s)						
		1	0.5	0.1	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.001
Data packets from the sender.	362	2057						
Data packets that represent real messages.	362	57						
Data packets that represent an attack.	0	2000						
Recipient data packets.	354	41						
Data packets tolerable by the victim.	0	890	889	882	781	375	0	
Data packets ignored by the victim.	0	1	2	9	110	516	891	
Data packets' delivery rate.	97.79	45.26	45.21	44.87	39.96	20.22	1.993	
Loss of the real data packets.	8	16						

Table 1

request the roadside radio transmit through the APDA protocol. According to this technique, once a node joins VANET and requests RSRT, RSRT updates its counter. A vehicle that has been requested checks the hop count.

If the number of hops matches, the automobile transforms into a verified node and is included into the network; otherwise, the next hop is updated. When a request is found to have already been made, RSRT discards it.

If demand > max-cap-counter

then display a faulty message

transmit it.

The authors of [5] provided research on denial-of-service attacks and their defenses in VANETs. They employed the frequency hopping spread spectrum approach, which lessens the impact of DoS attacks on VANETs. The message fluctuates in frequency when an attacker obstructs the communication route. The ability of this hopping between frequencies is provided by the following group of technological transitions: WI-MAX, WI-FI, UTRA-TDD, and Zig-Bee. They, together with multiple radio transceivers and channel and technology switching, are employed to lessen denial-of-service attacks.

The nodes of VANET with several receivers for receiving and sending messages is included into system of several radio receivers. Since the system can switch between transceivers in this instance, there is no longer any possibility of the network collapsing.

B. Black Hole Attacks Detection and mitigation Techniques:

An Optimized Enhanced Ad hoc On-demand Distance Vector (OEAODV) methodology for the detection of Gray and Black Hole assaults is presented by the authors in [25]. The sequence number and the hop count are two of the parameters of their proposed solution, OEAODV, and they are both included in the four key parameters. The Black Hole and Gray Hole exploit these two features to compromise the availability and integrity of the network. The network performance outputs represented by the other metrics in the study table have declined as a result of the first two being compromised. Therefore, by integrating these four (Th 1, Threshold for Seq; Th 2, Threshold for PDR; Th 3, Threshold for E2E; Th 4, Threshold for OH.) aspects and establishing the requirements for future Black Hole study, Algorithms 1 have the ability to determine the attack more effectively than previous methods. Figure 5 shows the model proposed by authors.

In [26] the author makes a little modification to the primary operational system used in the route discovery procedure of the AODV protocol by adding their own Red-AODV, when

Algorithm 1 Optimized enhanced ad hoc on-demand distance vector protocol

Input: Insecure data communication with Black Hole and Gray Hole attacks

Output: Secure data communication with Black Hole and Gray Hole attacks

```

1: Start
2: SN floods RREQ with Fake IP
3: If (IN reply back to Fake IP) OR (Seq > Th1) (GrayListing)
4:   SPN Affirmation
5:   Initialization of normal AODV route discovery
6:   Data packets Routing
7:   If (PDR < Th2 and E2E delay > Th3 and overhead(OH) > Th4) or (Blacklisting)
8:     MN Affirmation
9:     Blacklisting MN
10:    Addition of extra field in RREQ to encapsulate ID of MN for alarm
11:  else
12:    AODV ();
13:  end if
14: else
15:  start ();
16: end if
17: End

```

Algorithm of the method

a source node in Red-AODV wants to start sending data, it first stores the actual destination address for itself and then transmits an RREQ packet to each of its neighboring nodes, replacing the location of the end point in the packet with the CRC32 values. The neighbor node responds to the origin node by including the true location in the RREP packets if it is the end point itself or if it has the smallest route after receiving the RREQ packet. The temporary node simply passes the RREQ packet to the following node if both conditions are false. Numerous RREPs from various temporary nodes may be received by the source node. Figure 6 shows the workflow of Red-AODV.

Source will discard the RREP if the destination address is unexpected. A threshold is compared to RREP's sequence number if it contains a valid destination address.

If sequence number <= threshold;

The routing database is revised and RREP is authorized.

Or, if sequence number > threshold;

RREP is disposed of.

The authors of [27] suggested presenting and detecting a black hole attack (DPBHA). The two primary malicious characteristics of a BHA are exploited by the suggested DPBHA. Since the attacker node is assuming that it has a new route to the target, its RREP first has a greater sequence number and minimum hop count value. Second, every RREQ is always responded to by the attacker node first, without first consulting its routing table. To find and avoid BHA in VANET, reasonable adjustments are made to the AODV routing protocol's default operations to capitalize on these two qualities. The connectivity phase, detection phase, and preventive phase are the three main operating phases of the planned DPBHA. Framework of DPBHA can be seen in figure 7.

Fig. 5. Model proposed

Fig 6. workflow of Red-AODV

Fig.7 Framework of DPBHA

The system that is being analyzed begins operating, the structure is determined, and it is presumed that communication between the vehicles (nodes) has begun during the connectivity phase. In the middle step, the supposed harmful node—which has a 50% chance of being a black hole—is discovered. In the final stage, it is 100% certain that the suspected malicious node is a black hole node, and it ought to be disconnected from the network. Although the author has made some assumptions for the specified output to be achieved. Flowchart of DPBHA is in figure 8.

C. Jamming Attacks Detection and mitigation Techniques:

The authors of [28] presented DJVAN (Detecting Jamming Attacks in Vehicle Ad Hoc Networks), an algorithm for jamming detection in VANETs based on Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR). When an attacker successfully interrupts the correspondence between two nodes, the jamming situation is verified. As a result, the transmitter is unable to locate an open channel of communication for data transfer. All the packets will not reach the collecting node, even in the event that the recipient delivers data properly. DoS attacks are identified whether they are present or not when the packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) is low and its value falls below the specified threshold.

The following indicates a decline in PDR-

$$\text{Down-PDR} = \frac{\text{previous PDR} - \text{current PDR}}{\text{current time} - \text{previous time}}$$

Multiple Radio Transceivers: Using the concepts of multiple input multiple output architecture, the OBU is able to have numerous transceivers for sending and receiving messages.

Fig 8. Flowchart of DPBHA

In case of jamming assaults, this will enable the system to transition between transceivers. [29]

```

INPUT : Current_PDR= procedure_of_calcul_PDR,
          Down_PDR = calcul of down_PDR,
          State_jam = false
OUTPUT: announce_jam (position, State_jam,
                       current_time, Vector_V)

if Down_PDR  $\geq$  threshold_of_Down_speed then
  | State_jam = true;
end
if (0 < current_PDR  $\leq$  threshold_of_PDR) then
  | if Down_PDR > 0 then
  | | State_jam = true;
  | else
  | | State_jam = false;
  | end
end
if current_PDR = 0 then
  | State_jam = true;
end

Position = (x, y) ;
Get Current_time;
Lock Vector_V;
Return;

```

Algorithm for jamming attacks

Channel Signal Strength: By constantly giving the impression that the channel is busy, a reactive jammer aims to stop the genuine node from delivering packets to different nodes in the network. A method that tracks the overall duration of time the channel waited to become inactive, along with the location of the node and packet signal strength, is required to identify this kind of jamming. If jamming is happening in the channel, these data can be utilized to compare them to usual traffic times. The purpose of channel signal strength is to determine whether the data transmission value is within a certain threshold. A node is classified as a jammer if the threshold value is exceeded by its maximum packet. On the other hand, if a given threshold value is smaller than the packet value, it might be recognized by not a jammer as it might be the consequence of poor communication signals.

VI. CONCLUSION:

The VANET network, which shares information between vehicles to increase the security of the car, its occupants, and drivers, was emphasized in this study. Because of the fundamental characteristics of VANET systems and their great degree of accessibility, these networks are very vulnerable to attacks, with availability attacks being the most dangerous across the board. To assist save the driver and any occupants of the car, it is crucial to determine the attack's defensive remedies. Numerous studies and attempts have been undertaken to offer security solutions for VANETs, but they have not been able to give a comprehensive answer since they have applied typical security methods without taking into account the unique characteristics of the VANET environment.

Furthermore, these remedies are only able to lessen the attack's intensity. The best defense against attacks that take down critical network infrastructures and impact users is early threat detection. Thus, it is advised installing the proper

security measures on the networks, such as monitoring software's, to keep an eye on network traffic and send notifications for unusual activity. In this work, I have reviewed and compiled the several potential fixes for availability attacks that have been developed by various researchers. I want to construct simulations for a few VANET applications in order to verify the suggested remedies, as well as give a way to identify and stop these attacks in VANET in the future.

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